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Human Action Sequence Prediction for (Re)configuring Machine Tools

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Abstract

In industrial production systems, (re)configuration of machines mainly depends on the expertise of the human operators. Through human motion capture, the actions and intentions of the operator can be recorded with body and eye gaze trackers. The inexperienced and non-proficient workers may benefit from the captured data to perform similar tasks proficiently by determining their intentions and simulating their actions. However, there is a lack of a predefined set of actions that may vary the intentions and human actions from user to user and task to task. Therefore, it is essential to recognize and classify the motion data for specific actions and tasks in accordance with the intentions of an expert. Since manual annotation of motion data requires substantial resources and effort, the labeling time can eventually be minimized with automatic recognition of human actions. This work presents an automated human action sequence prediction method, particularly for (re)configuration of die tool for progressive forming. The result is compared and analyzed with manually recognized human actions. Results show potential for creating a knowledge base system that comprises expertise on how skilled human operators perform non-structured tasks that could facilitate nonskilled workers to perform learned actions on the shop floor.

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1. Introduction

Today, there are rapid changes in product demand and production systems which require continuous and effective (re)configuration at different industrial levels such as macro-level, meso-level and micro-level. These levels require varying human expertise for resilient production system in complete value chain [1]. In this respect, the macro and meso-level (re)configurations are mostly dependent upon soft skills attained from qualification and knowledge. However, shop floor (re)configurations require additional skills developed gradually with hands on experience. They can also vary from process to process and individual to individual. It might be hard to find standard (re)configuration procedures [2].

Machine tools (re)configuration, especially for progressive forming may require precise execution which can lead to a complex process. The need for (re)configuration may be

triggered from various factors such as changes in raw material, tool wear, tool misalignment or product specifications. In small and medium enterprises where there might not be a standardized (re)configuration process in place, the expertise of the human operator may become crucial in ensuring a smooth transition between different configurations [3].

Inefficient (re)configuration may increase non-value adding activities that might result in non-resilient manufacturing value chains. To address this, a situation and fault detection system may be designed that classify worker situations from the worker's action so as to determine concrete (re)configuration actions and strategies.

Through human motion capture, the actions and intentions of the operator can be recorded with body and eye gaze trackers [4]. The inexperienced and non-proficient workers may benefit from the captured data to perform similar tasks proficiently by determining their intentions and simulating their actions. Also, a knowledge data base acquired from an expert can be created

that may further assist a non-expert user to (re)configure machine tools in a complex system, such as progressive forming press machine.

2. State of the art

With the current unprecedented uncertainties, reconfigurable manufacturing systems are being considered as a potential alternative for adapting to the market dynamics and product demands cf. [3]. A reconfigurable manufacturing system refers to a manufacturing system that comprises rapid change either in the software or hardware component or both cf. [5]. According to Koren [5], this rapid adaptability of the manufacturing system with a sudden changing market is characterized by its diagnosability, convertibility, flexibility, integrability, and modularity.

In order to ease the reconfiguration effort in manufacturing industry, there is a need of reconfigurability enablers [6]. Mo et al. [7] propose semantic model and knowledge graphs as manufacturing reconfiguration enablers. The semantic model and knowledge graphs support cognitive process of drawing a decision in reconfiguration of system. Later Mo et al. [8] combine knowledge graphs with simulation environment using artificial intelligence and digital twin in order to improve decision making process for reconfiguration. Albus and Huber [9] propose a model for reconfiguration with additional constraints allowing company specific problems for flexible production systems. Similarly, Makssoud et al. [10] derive a mathematical model to address reconfiguration needs of transferring machining lines.

However, implementing a reconfigurable manufacturing system is challenging; for example, Rösiö and Säfsten [11] identify design complexity and knowledge acquisition as constraints. Other factors, such as cost-effectiveness and customization variety, are also identified as critical factors [3].

A human behavior analysis that involves, e.g., how industrial actions are performed and their relation to precedencies, seems promising for planning processes. Several efforts are carried out to analyze human motion behaviors in industrial environments. Agethen et al. [12] analyze walk motions in an automotive industrial environment and investigate significant deviation of actual human motions compared to the planned process. Similarly, Manns et al. [13] investigate the variation of reach motion in an industrial assembly process. These approaches consider human motions only from the third-person perspective. In [14], an extended approach that combines human action and intention is proposed based on human body motion capture and eye focus tracker. The use of several sensors for human motion behavior analysis and action classification is presented in several works e.g. [15,16].

Furthermore, human action prediction and classification are described on different levels, with basic actions or cognitive actions. These definition scopes depend on the application and the techniques employed for modeling. Modeling techniques such as deep learning require intensive motion data segmentation and labeling during the pre-processing cf. [17]. In contrast, the segmentation and labeling can be automated using probabilistic models such as Gaussian Mixture Models

(GMM) [4]. According to the review analysis of Menolotto et al. [18], the choice of model depends on the sensor and data type. In this aspect, several motion capture systems have been tested by various research groups. These human motion capture systems can be optical, inertial, mechanical, magnetic, or acoustic technologies [19]. Optical sensor-based human motion capture is demonstrated using three-dimensional camera systems with depth information (e.g., ZEDi [20]) or multiple camera systems fixed at different orientations (e.g., Optitrack® [21]). According to Nagymáté and Kiss [21] the feasibility of a camera system for industrial human motion capture depends on the light, reflection, level of occlusion, and space. Alternatively, Inertial Measurement Units (IMUs) are used for industrial human motion capturing [16].

Human action sequence prediction involves capturing human motion, e.g., IMUs, which are defined at different granularity levels. For example, Deuse et al. [22] follow an MTM-based definition for describing operations such as reaching, tightening, moving, and inserting. According to the semantic definition of actions described in [22], a worker who extends their arm to a specific location to interact with a specific object is known as a *reach to an object*; when the fingers grasp or take an object, it will be extended to *pick the object*. Then, if the worker aligns an object at a specific location and places or fits it inside, it is known as an *inserting* action. The action that involves the rotation of the screw while applying force until it is fastened is the *tightening* action.

However, there is a lack of a predefined set of actions that may vary the intentions and human actions from user to user and task to task. Therefore, it is essential to recognize and classify the motion data for specific actions and tasks in accordance with the intentions of an expert. Since manual annotation of motion data requires substantial resources and effort, the labeling time can eventually be minimized with automatic recognition of human actions.

3. Objective

This work examines whether human action sequence and frequency remains consistent for each press (re)configuration by applying automated human action sequence prediction method. This may allow non-skilled workers to learn how to perform non-structured shop floor actions, particularly for (re)configuring a die tool for progressive forming.

With this examination, it is aimed to confirm the following conditions: (i) investigate if the number of actions are same for each press (re)configuration, (ii) determine if there are unique actions performed during (re)configuration of the presses and (iii) verify if similar sequence of actions exist for all the presses.

Fig. 1. Proposed human motion sequence prediction method for machine tool (re)configuration

4. Methodology

The proposed methodology and workflow for human action sequence prediction is depicted in Fig. 1. Firstly, human motions are captured with IMU sensors. The captured data is then analyzed in order to detect and label actions such as walking, hammering, and assembling. Further, the data is processed with a tool that automatically detects and annotates sequence of actions performed by the worker. This sequence is useful in storing as a knowledge-base, that might be advantageous for a non-expert aiming to perform similar tasks.

4.1. Human motion capture

IMU sensors are attached to the body of an expert in order to capture actions while (re)configuring the progressive forming press machine. In total 17 body segments are covered and captured. The captured motions are stored in Bio-vision hierarchy (BVH) which comprises a human skeleton tree of twenty-two joints. Root starts from the hips comprising position and orientation data, whereas other joints comprise rotational motions only.

Additionally, gaze sensors are put on by the worker so as to measure the intention or field of focus while performing the tasks. This provides precise visibility to performed actions from an expert point of view. A video camera is also placed to record the overall setup from a broader aspect.

4.2. Manual action detection and labeling

The manual labeling for actions is performed by the human expert using markers inside the MVN Analyze® tool with the help of the world scene view captured from the front view camera and the worker's perspective view from the eye tracker optical sensor. Based on these multi-sensor data, the worker information is analyzed initially to understand the human situation and to detect the performed actions, and then these actions are labeled with the initial and final key frames of the action. The labeled actions are evaluated for their sequence, repetition (frequency) and durations.

4.3. Automated worker's action sequence detection and annotation

Since human motion capturing and analysis is a time-consuming, costly, and computationally demanding process, automating the action sequence detection and annotation is required. Interpreting human motion into a meaningful process requires fast data processing, and this can be achieved using feature dimensionality reduction. In the state of the art, human motion features were successfully reduced using principal component analysis (PCA) cf. [13]. Applying approach proposed by Manns et al. [13], position and orientation of each joint motion data is analyzed and reduced to the principal components. Accordingly, the PCA analysis converged with forty features out of one hundred forty-one features.

Fig. 2. Experimental setup for human motion capturing during press tool (re)configuration for multi-stage progressive forming press

5. Experimental Setup

Experimental setup to record human actions is depicted in Fig. 2. The human actions are recorded in industrial environment to (re)configure machine tools associated with multi-stage progressive forming press, used to produce deep-drawn components for automobile and heating industry. The worker is an expert for (re)configuring the machine with an experience of more approximately 10 years. The worker is able to (re)configure machine tool for 3 stages.

XSENS Awinda IMU sensors are employed to capture the human actions at the speed of 60 frames per second. Considering the hips as root, 17 sensors are placed on complete body that includes pelvis, upper legs, lower legs, foot, shoulders, upper arms, lower arms, hands, sternum and head. The system captured approximately 250,000 data frames in total. Eye gaze of worker is captured with Pupil Invisible eye tracking glasses in order to get insights about the intention of worker while performing certain tasks. Additionally, Panasonic HC-X1 video camera is positioned to capture complete scene. The camera video is rendered with VLC player, data from eye gaze sensor is assessed with Pupil Invisible Companion software, and motion capture data is perceived and analyzed with MVN Analyze software.

The operation processes start from walking to pick parts such as wrench. It ends by insertion of four M8 screws into the screw hole and tightening. In the intermediate, five motions are identified by an expert as summarized in Table 1. According to action motions defined in MOSIM framework¹, “walk” is “to walk from one position to another”. “Screw in” is combination of “fasten” and “tighten” and defined as “to place a screw in a hole and screw it two turns” and “joining parts by a screw or by a screw like connector (e.g. nut) using a tool”. “Screw out” is “use wrench to remove nut/screw”. “Putting down” is “place” defined as “to place a grabbed object in a position different from its original position”. “Picking up” is “Pick part” defined as “to grab an object and remove it from a position.

¹ https://github.com/mercedes-benz/MOSIM_Core/tree/master

Table 1: Identified actions during the (re)configuration of progressive forming tool presses.

Code	Abbreviation	Explanation
0	WA	Walking
1	SI	Screw in / Fasten and Tighten
2	SO	Screw out / Unfasten
3	PU	Picking up / Pick part
4	PD	Putting down / Place

6. Result

6.1. Manual segmentation

Some actions that were difficult to interpret and replicate in the automated action detection and annotation process, e.g., wiping and inspection, are not analyzed. The average, maximum, and minimum action durations are depicted in Table 3. This shows that the die punch's put-down, pick up, walk, and assembly are the most frequently observed actions. Similarly, the screwing that involves insertion and tightening of the screw took a longer duration. This has been caused due to the number of screws required for each press dies (i.e., four screws for each die punch). In contrast, picking up parts is the fastest operation observed.

To further understand, the number of actions, types of action sequences, and unique actions are explicitly analyzed. Accordingly, to see if there is a similarity between the sequences of the actions, action sequences in each scenario are defined using codes assigned for each action. In this aspect, the different granularities of the actions are considered.

For example, if action sequence (AS) for press 1(P1) involves the sequence of *walk* → *pick up* → *walk* → *pick up* → *put down*, it can be represented as $AS^{P1} = 03034$. Accordingly, the action sequences for each press are represented as AS^{P1} , AS^{P2} , and AS^{P3} , respectively. These codes are based on the definitions given in Table 1. Following this concept, the human action sequence prediction and annotation method generated action sequences that can represent each press. This is desired to study if the sequences in each press tool are consistent or not. Similarly, the number of actions and duration are desired for

further study. Table 2 summarizes the number of actions, their uniqueness, and the sample of the sequence.

Table 2: Frequency and sequence comparison observed in the manual labelling (X = undetected action).

	No. of Actions	Unique action	Type of sequences
Press I	205	8	$AS^{P1} = 030434340343434$
Press II	160	8	$AS^{P2} = X3043434343434$
Press III	200	8	$AS^{P3} = 030X43434X343434$

6.2. Automated segmentation and annotation

Once sufficient knowledge is collected from the manual analysis, automated action segmentation and annotation are followed. This step included the feature reduction using principal component analysis (PCA). Accordingly, the features are reduced from 141 to 5 principal components with an explainable variance of 99.83% (see Fig. 3). Once the principal features are identified, these principal features are used for classifying human actions into sets of classes using statistical-based machine learning algorithms (namely, kMeans and

Fig. 3. Explained variance ratio versus PCA Components

Table 3: Action frequency and duration comparison of manual and automated action detection

Action type	Manual				Automated			
	Frequency	Duration			Frequency	Duration		
		Max	Min	Av		Max	Min	Av
PD	15	2454	202	824	49	3	173	58
PU	26	516	20	143	18	113	35343	9417
SI	23	8729	258	4056	9	54	1387	769
WA	26	1611	40	356	11	188	483	270
SO	9	18680	96	3307	11	61	162	104

GMM) to identify the best fitting model for analyzing the action sequences and durations. The best fitting model is selected based on Silhouette Scores following the works of Virtanen et al. [23]. Accordingly, the models yielded a performance score of 0.58 for the model based on kMeans and 0.37 for the GMM models. Based on this, the kMeans model was selected for further analysis.

The motions segmented using kMeans are classified into action classes based on the best similarity or matching score compared to the manually labeled actions. Then, the annotated actions, i.e., both manual and automated action annotations, are evaluated for their sequence matching using existing sequence matcher algorithms². The similarity ratio for both sequences is evaluated for several action sizes. As depicted in Fig. 4, the actions start from 1 element and extend up to 5 actions. As the number of actions increases, the similarity of the actions is decreased. In this figure, 1 action represents PU, 2 actions [PU, PD], 3 actions [PU, PD, WA], 4 actions represent [PU, PD, WA, SO], and 5 actions represent [PU, PD, WA, SO, SI].

The action frequencies for each press tool in the (re)configuration are depicted in the Table 4. This table compares each press's frequencies and analyzes their similarity ratio. Accordingly, the put-down (PD) motion yielded 100% similarity for press tool III, while in press II, the put-down motion is over-predicted with the automated annotation. Similarly, the minimum similarity ratio is achieved in press I for walk motion. In this aspect, the action prediction is unable to distinguish the walk motions.

7. Discussion

7.1. Result interpretation

The results are interpreted based on action types, frequency, sequence, and durations. The action duration describes the time required to complete the action. The higher variation in action duration across different presses shows the difficulty of the operation in terms of the reachability, the process or external disturbances. Accordingly, higher durations are observed during the action of screwing out, and it is caused due to errors and misalignment of the tool, tolerance errors, and oily tools, which has required the worker to perform hammering and wiping.

Fig. 4. Comparison of manual and automated action sequence similarity with the number of detected actions

Similarly, the frequency variation observed across the press (re)configuration indicates the probability of action repetitions for similar jobs but different parts. The variations in the frequency are caused again due to tolerance errors, which require additional activities and tools in the meantime. The action sequence indicates the precedence of actions one before the other. The variation of sequences is observed in the tests and they evidently show that the (re)configuration process of progressive forming tool is skill dependent and the probability of variation from one press to another even though they have similar intentions and tasks.

7.2. Result comparison and description

As shown in the result sections, the frequencies of the actions varied during the (re)configuration of each press. A huge variation is observed in picking parts, which accounts for about 8%, and the lowest variation is observed in the disassembly process, which is about 3% variation. This implies, even though the overall intention remains consistent, the action frequencies and sequences were altered. The sequence analysis reveals that several factors altered the sequences, including errors, misalignment of the tools, dirtiness, and difficulty reaching the target position during the process.

Table 4. Analysis for action frequency for each press tool (re)configuration and their similarity ratio (automated to manual ratio).

	Press I Tool		Press II tool		Press III tool		Similarity ratio		
	Manual	Automated	Manual	Automated	Manual	Automated	Press I tool	Press II tool	Press III tool
PD	15	2	11	26	13	13	13%	236%	100%
PU	26	10	14	5	16	1	38%	36%	6%
SI	4	2	5	2	4	4	50%	40%	100%
WA	19	0	15	9	20	2	0%	60%	10%
SO	2	2	5	8	2	1	100%	160%	50%

² <https://docs.python.org/3/library/difflib.html> (last accessed 20.04.2024)

The overall result proves the initially proposed hypothesis regarding action duration, sequence, and frequency is valid for planning machine tool (re)configuration in an industrial environment. This is crucial for assisting workers in following the best practice sequence of operation. The interpreted result shows:

- Human action duration can vary from one action to another.
- Action sequences are not entirely dependent on the intention of the task but also on the worker's intention and attention.
- The frequency of human actions is varying for similar intentions in the given machine tool (re)configuration.

Moreover, the presented approach is skill-dependent, operations that are associated with the level of experience or cause-effect knowledge.

8. Conclusion and Outlook

The work presents a method for automated human action sequence annotation that can assist workers in performing machine tool (re)configuration for progressive forming press based on cause-and-effect analysis. The results are described in terms of duration, sequence, and repetition frequency. The results are compared and analyzed with manually recognized human actions. A future outlook involves expanding the proposed methodology to encompass other machine processes. Accordingly, the proposed method evidently shows a knowledge base system that comprises action type, frequency, duration, and sequence can be created based on human motion data capturing that will help industrial experts to easily transfer skills and knowledge for performing actions whenever it is required to perform non-structured tasks.

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